

Communication and Work Environment on Employee Performance with Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable

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Abstract

The original aim of this research was to find out whether communication and workplace are risk factors for staff performance and the staff job satisfaction. A sample of 189 people was used in this study and statistical partial least squares (PLS) analysis was used. From this research it is known that: (1) there is no impact of communication on staff performance; (2) the workplace has no exclusive impact on staff performance; (3) communication has an exclusive impact on job satisfaction; (4) the workplace has a direct impact on job satisfaction; (5) job satisfaction has no personal impact on staff performance; (6) indirectly communication does not affect staff performance with job satisfaction as an intervening variable; and (7) indirectly the workplace does not affect staff performance with job satisfaction as the intervening variable.

1. Introduction

In fact, the staff work for organizations that specialize in transportation. Effective organizational management requires qualified and trained staff to enhance employee performance for smooth management functions. Retail companies or transportation companies experience stiff competition. This is due to the increasing public demand for service consumers. Companies can also meet the needs of the people. In addition to a wide range of connectivity, the company also offers a wide range of customer services that are adapted to customer requirements and requirements.

Since today's life is busy with complex daily tasks, it is important that we adapt to developments and make things faster, more efficient and easier. In this dynamic environment that requires fast and efficient delivery, people need to use and provide transparent services to

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implement their software. This encourages the creation of mail orders or customer service. The best thing about this company is that it is easy for people to reach the delivery point which the exclusive carriers cannot.

Employee performance is the performance of work carried out by individuals or groups in an organization according to their roles and responsibilities to achieve organizational goals in accordance with respective laws without violating these laws.(Sutrisno, 2010). Company staff is called efficient if their performance meets or exceeds the principles or conditions set by the organization. Work environment, job satisfaction, employee performance, motivation, work environment are factors that affect employee performance(Rosmina, 2021). Good communication can increase understanding, cooperation, job satisfaction and productivity(Noor, 2020). The work environment can create cooperative relationships between people in that environment(Moekijat, 2010). Job satisfaction is determined by various factors related to employee performance such as communication, work environment and job satisfaction(Ahmad & Si, 2019).

JNE is an advertising and marketing company based in Jakarta. JNE's work results are greatly affected by how its staff carry out the work process. Currently PT. JNE Medan Branch is competing to develop delivery and courier services as well as other logistics. Employee performance has a significant impact on the performance of PT. JNE Medan Branch. The decision to evaluate the performance of the JNE Branch for 2021 can be observed from the key performance indicator (KPI) according to the ability of staff to achieve company goals. The performance results of PT. JNE for 2021 is shown in Table 1 below.

Table 1.
Employee Performance Evaluation at PT. JNE Medan Branch
In June-November 2021

NO	Rating Scale	Month					
		June	July	August	September	October	November
1	special	20	21	22	19	20	22
2	Above competency	17	18	17	18	19	20
3	According Competency	9	5	5	6	7	5
4	Lack of Competency	4	4	6	6	5	1
5	Does not meet competency	2	4	2	3	1	4
Total		52	52	52	52	52	52

Source: HRD PT. JNE Medan Main Branch, data processed by researchers

PT. JNE Medan Main Branch is committed to improving employee performance so that the company can achieve maximum performance. PT. JNE Medan Main Branch in enhancing employee performance is by supporting staff to achieve predetermined performance, ensuring employee performance, and the company ensuring staff commitment to their work. Based on a survey conducted by researchers to several staff of PT. JNE Medan Branch regarding the communication that exists within the company produced results that can be seen that internal communication is not going well. because there are still obstacles in communicating information from managers to staff. Obstacles come in many forms, for example, information originating from top managers cannot directly reach lower staff because the information obtained still has to go through the heads of departments. Therefore, there is a chance that the information conveyed by the manager or top management of the company will change or not match what the manager conveyed with what the

head of management conveyed. This is understandable, because all the media used to send messages will change according to personal needs or interests.

Factors that affect employee performance have the smallest variable of 4,35. Incomplete scores for communication and other variables that affect employee performance. Based on previous research, the researcher interviewed several staff at the Medan branch of PT.JNE in terms of communication, the effect of internal communication does not seem to be fully reflected. Because there are still obstacles in communicating information from top to bottom. The difficulty is the number of paths to traverse. There is frequent miscommunication between staff and between staff and customers which is a common thing at the Medan Head Office. Other problems can be found in the working environment of the staff, which can lead to poor employee performance.

Cahyaningrum (2019) examines the effects of compensation and the work environment on employee performance using job satisfaction as a variable that intervenes with other variables in the research. Cahyaningrum researched at PT. Sampurna Kuningan Juwana, Patti Regency, which has the final result of the research, namely that there is a positive and negative relationship between employee performance compensation and the work environment, and job satisfaction is used as an intervening variable between the two variables. In addition, Arianto(2020)examines the effect of strategic leadership and communication on job satisfaction as a variable that intervenes with X and Y variables. In his research as an intervention variable, leadership and communication In his research on how it positively and significantly affects work and job satisfaction. Previous research has shown that communication and the work environment have a significant impact on employee performance and job satisfaction is an intervention variable. Most researchers examine the independent variable (X) directly from the intervention variable (Z), in this case job satisfaction. In accordance with the problem, the research hypothesis is formulated as follows:

H1 : Communication has an impact on job satisfaction of PT. JNE Medan Main Branch.

H2: The work environment has a direct impact on the job satisfaction of PT. JNE Medan Main Branch.

H3: Communication has a direct impact on the performance of PT. JNE Medan Main Branch

H4: The work environment has a direct impact on employee performance among PT. JNE Medan Main Branch.

H5: Job satisfaction has a direct impact on employee performance for PT. JNE Medan Main Branch.

H6: Communication as a staff risk factor that has an indirect impact on employee performance and job satisfaction as an intervention variable at PT. JNE Medan Main Branch.

H7: The work environment has an indirect impact on employee performance and job satisfaction as an intervention variable at PT. JNE Medan Main Branch

2. Materials and Methods

The object of this research is PT. Tiki Jalan Nugraha Ekakurir (JNE) Medan Main Branch Jl. Sisingmangaraja Km 10.5 Amplas Trade Center Complex, Medan City, North Sumatra with postal code 20149. In this case the researcher used a random sampling method and obtained 189 responses. Data collection methods in this research used questionnaires, surveys, literature reviews and data analysis using validity checks and data reliability checks. Statistical analysis using the Partial Least Square (PLS) model.

3. Results and Discussions

Overview of Research Informants

Table 2.
Characteristics of Informants Based on Age

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	21-30 Years	107	56.6	56.6	56.6
	31 – 40 Years	44	23.3	23.3	79.9
	41 – 50 Years	27	14.3	14.3	94.2
	> 51 Years	11	5.8	5.8	100.0
	Total	189	100.0	100.0	

Source: PLS Analysis Results, 2022

107 informants or 56.6% were 21-30 years old, 44 people or 23.3% were 31-40 years old, 27 people or 14.3% were 41-50 years old, and informants who were >51 years old totaled 11 informants or 5.8%.

Table 3.
Characteristics of Informants by Gender

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Man	124	65.6	65.6	65.6
	Woman	65	34.4	34.4	100.0
	Total	189	100.0	100.0	

Source: PLS Analysis Results, 2022

Male informants were 124 people or 65.6% and female informants were 65 people or 34.4%.

Table 4.
Characteristics of Informants Based on Length of Service

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	< 5 years	119	63.0	63.0	63.0
	5 – 10 years	49	25.9	25.9	88.9
	11 – 20 years	19	10.1	10.1	98.9
	> 21 years	2	1.1	1.1	100.0
	Total	189	100.0	100.0	

Source: PLS Analysis Results, 2022

A total of 119 workers (63%) worked for less than 5 years, 49 workers (25.9%) worked for 5-10 years, and 19 workers (10.1%) worked for 11-20 years, and more than 21 years. and 2 staff (1.1%) working more than 21 years.

Convergent validity

Figure 1.
First Outer Loading
Source: PLS Analysis Results, 2022

Convergent Validity construct indicators on the communication variable (X1) based on Convergent Validity construct indicators that do not meet the loading factor values are questions 1,2,3,4,9,10 and 11. Work environment variable (X2) Convergent Validity construct indicators that do not meet the loading values question factors 1,5,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17, 19,20 and 21. Job satisfaction variable (Z1) Convergent Validity construct indicators that do not meet the value of loading factor questions 2 and 10 .Variable employee performance(Y) which does not meet the loading factor values for questions 1,2,4,10,12,13,14 and 17.

Discriminant Validity

Table 5.
Cronbach's Alpha Test

	Cronbach's Alpha value
Employee performance (Y)	0.909
Communication (X1)	0.864
Work environment (X2)	0.911
Job Satisfaction (Z1)	0.907

Source: PLS Analysis Results, 2022

Cronbach's α value for each variable in this research exceeds 0.7, indicating that the configuration variable has shown a high level of reliability.

Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Table 6.
Discriminant Validity Test

	Average AVE score
Employee performance (Y)	0,486
Communication (X1)	0,558
Work environment (X2)	0,520
Job Satisfaction (Z1)	0,442

Source: PLS Analysis Results, 2022

All values for each variable were found to be greater than the acceptable threshold of 0.5. Therefore, the instrument is valid.

Composite Reliability

Table 7.
Testcronbach's Alpha

	Composite Reliability Value
Employee performance (Y)	0.885
Communication (X1)	0.809
Work environment (X2)	0.892
Job Satisfaction (Z1)	0.885

Source: PLS Analysis Results, 2022

Those values are proven to be greater than 0.7, indicating that the variable structure is proven to have a high degree of reliability.

*Structural Equation Model (SEM) Analysis Test**Direct Effects of Communication on Employee Performance*

Statistical significance of 0.345 was achieved by testing the hypothesis of the exclusive impact of communication on employee performance. Below 1.97287 (t standing 0.345 < t table 1.97287), the p value is 0.730 > 0.05. This shows that changes in communication do not directly affect employee performance because the information provided by superiors becomes data that describes the strength of the network if the information arrives without any miscommunication in it. PT. JNE Medan branch cannot provide work ideas/vision PT managers do not respond properly to messages and information sent by staff with an average score of 4.25 Managers cannot present clear issues the average homogeneous score of the organization is 4.29 with resource policies insufficient human. This is because the staff cannot solve problems in the work environment.

The success of a company is affected by the relationship of its staff. Based on Kalfried Knapp (Akbar et al., 2018), communication is human relations through language (words) and linguistic

symbols (similar to non-linguistic symbols). This process can be carried out face-to-face or through other media (written, oral, visual). now, intrinsic job performance (Akbar et al., 2018) refers to work outcomes and work attitudes that are achieved by carrying out tasks and responsibilities over a certain period of time.

Direct effect of work environment on employee performance

A statistical significance of 0.023 was achieved by testing the hypothesis of the direct impact of the work environment on employee performance. Less than 1.97287 (standing $t_{0.023} < t_{table} 1.97287$) and P value $0.982 > 0.05$. This shows that changes in the work environment do not directly affect employee performance. Quantitative test results are supported by descriptive statistics on changes in working conditions. PT. JNE Medan Branch tells most of the information. does not heed orders and instructions from superiors and interferes with the work of staff with an average scale of 4.32, desk layout is not easy with an average scale of 4.35, if the work environment does not support work, there will be many errors in the work results. leads to bad results.

According to Lustono & Desy (2019), performance from the origin of what can be achieved by individuals or groups to achieve goals according to their roles and responsibilities in the organization. We are responsible for conducting business legally, without violating rules and regulations. The work environment is very crucial for staff, pay attention to a good work environment creating a good work environment affects staff satisfaction, and a good work environment makes staff feel confident and comfortable in working effectively and efficiently (Son, 2021).

Direct Effects of Communication on Job Satisfaction

To test that the communication model has a direct impact on job satisfaction, a value of 7.725 is obtained, greater than 1.97287 (static $t_{7.725} > t_{table} 1.97287$), P value $0.000 < 0.05$. This shows that changes in communication affect job satisfaction. Correlation test results are strengthened by data describing the interdependent variables. Most of the responses agree with Question 6, which has a high score of 4.47 to indicate staff communication at PT. JNE can recruit other staff and improve employee performance. Job satisfaction is achieved because most of the staff accept the payment system available at PT. JNE Medan Branch, which upholds the principle of equality between staff, obtained a total of 4.46 points in these 4 questions. The average answer is 4.12.

The average informant score indicates how satisfied staff are with their work. Because work meets their expectations. With a score of 4.46, leaders often focus on motivation and the work people do. Communication is very important to achieve organizational goals. Communication about a person's needs, wants, and attitudes. Specific communications include communication with superiors, contributions from subordinates, social networks, social networks and relationships. Confidential reports often include both personal and non-personal information. flows through a special path (Indahningrum et al., 2020).

Direct Effect of the Work Environment on Job Satisfaction

Testing the hypothesis that the work environment has a direct impact on job satisfaction is $4.836 > 1.97287$ (Statistics $4.836 > Table 1.97287$), P value $0.000 < 0.05$. This shows that changes in the work environment have an exclusive impact on job satisfaction. the quantitative test that will take place is supported by the narrative statistics of communication exchange, where most of the informants are parents. Yes Question 15, homogeneous average 4.69. the work environment

supports their work because it is relatively clear using an average of 3.66 and the space provided by large companies uses a homogeneous average of 4.24 with a score of 4.46, the company supports work and creates a positive work environment. Their job satisfaction is mostly related to the employer's acceptance of the payment system available for PT.

The work environment affects the performance of all staff tasks around it. This results in a dilemma similar to the high error at work. These products are not good for the work environment and must be avoided, so that staff are satisfied with their work environment, it is necessary to cooperate more towards achieving the goal of a good and comfortable working environment.(M. & Yuniara, 2022).

Direct Effects of Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance

Examining certain examples of job satisfaction on employee performance, we find a statistical value of 1.275 which is lower than 1.97287 ($t_{static} 0.023 < t_{table} 1.97287$). $0.203 > 0.05$. This shows that job satisfaction does not specifically affect employee performance. because many workers do not have the opportunity to learn to develop skills with a 4.04 GPA, many do not excel in this field. The average score was homogeneous 4.55, the average score of staff who failed to meet the manager's goals was 4.40, the average score was 4.40, the average score of staff who failed to resolve problems in the office was 4.42.

This study provides that high job satisfaction is not a factor that points to increased staff productivity or increased productivity in the organization, distributing negative and unproductive work for staff.

Indirect Effects of Communication on Employee Performance with Job Satisfaction as an Intervention Variable

Modeling the experience of staff communication performance, using job satisfaction as an intervention variable, the researchers found a statistical value of 1.161, which was lower than 1.97287 (constant $t 1.161 < Table 1.97287$). Value $-0.246 > 0.05$. Communication does not exclusively affect employee performance, but provides a surprising variable in job satisfaction. The results of the relationship test are strengthened using data that describe the interdependent variables. Most PT informants have a high level of communication. They did not respond well to information and news, with an average of 4.25, and managers did not provide information about their jobs. The average homogeneous value for organizational activities and processes is 4.29, and the average homogeneous value for the variable job satisfaction is 4.04, or the time the staff is unable to complete the job. Homogeneous means 4, 40 which stated that workers neglected their work and were not imprisoned. If the average priority of work is 4.49 and the staff work ratio is 4.42, then the staff cannot solve problems in the office.

To enhance staff satisfaction, staff must feel that their work is valued. It can be said that job satisfaction varies from person to person. Certain satisfactions depend on taking appropriate action. This is due to individual differences. The more suitable a job uses a person's interests, the higher the level of satisfaction. conversely, when work is out of sync with individual expectations, satisfaction decreases (Arisca et al., 2019).

Indirect Effect of Work Environment on Employee Performance with Job Satisfaction as an intervention variable

Judging from the variable job satisfaction, there will be testing due to the work environment on employee performance statistic $1.355 < 1.97287$ (t statistic $1.355 < \text{table } t \ 1.97287$) $0.176 > P$ value 0.05. This shows that the work environment does not directly affect employee performance but is a latent variable of job satisfaction. Special test results are confirmed by showing PT. JNE Maiden Branch does not pay much attention to all orders and instructions from top management and its poor performance is 4.46.

In addition to statistical data on work environment variables, most of the informants agreed to use work environment variables, with a homogeneous value of 4.47 indicating that the dominant staff was PT. The JNE Maiden branch is not sensitive to orders and instructions from management. origin configuration, a homogeneous average of 4.32 is obtained when the bank is not installed properly, so an average of 4.35 comes from measurement errors, because the device in the operating environment does not support the operating system. Between productivity changes and poor performance, and disparities in job satisfaction, many staff lack opportunities to develop skills, with an average homogeneous score of 4.04, but most do not.

If the average homogeneous score is 4.55 and the staff gets 4.40 and does not meet the targets set by the manager, then the staff is not managed. If the average score is 4.40, staff cannot prioritize tasks using a score of 4.49, and when the average score is 4.42, staff are unable to solve problems that arise as the device in the operating environment does not support the operating system. Between productivity changes and poor performance, and disparities in job satisfaction, many staff lack opportunities to develop skills, with an average homogeneous score of 4.04, but most do not.

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The work environment is a situation or situation where an individual motivates staff to fulfill their obligations and responsibilities and carry out their duties (Banjari, 2020). A supportive work environment helps staff feel comfortable and relaxed. As a result, staff feel satisfied with their jobs because they can adapt to conditions with a better work environment (Firdaus, 2021).

4. Conclusion

This study produced seven conclusions, namely first, communication does not personally affect the performance of employees of PT. JNE main branch Medan, the two work environments do not personally affect the performance of employees of PT. JNE Medan primary branch. Personal collaboration communication with job satisfaction PT. JNE main branch Medan. The work environment personally affects the job satisfaction of PT. JNE Medan primary branch. Job satisfaction does not exclusively affect the performance of PT. JNE Medan primary branch. indirectly communication does not affect employee performance with job satisfaction being the intervention variable of PT. JNE's main branch in Medan and in no particular way the work environment does not affect employee performance with job satisfaction being the intervention variable for PT. JNE primary branch Medan.

PT. JNE Medan Branch can be judged based on the number of staff still working at the company and their level of performance. The highest average value is 4.77 and the lowest value is 3.10. Many staff are able to solve work problems. Communication staff of PT. JNE Medan Branch can be evaluated as long as the number of staff whose communication in the work environment suggests other staff in the office uses the highest score of 4.77 and the lowest score is 3.10. Some staff have difficulty communicating and creating correlations with co-workers. Some staff interact using the following when providing information or making crucial decisions. The working environment of PT. JNE Medan Branch routinely invites partners for lunch, communicates between staff, increases staff satisfaction and performance, and can be estimated according to the maximum number of 4.69 workers. A low score of 3.33 indicates that most workers have difficulty using public transportation to return to their work environment. PT. JNE Medan branch provides the number of staff who receive a salary payment system. JNE Medan Branch is an example of equal distribution of work energy with the highest score of 4.46 and the lowest score of 4.04. The staff develop their skills and are motivated by the direct and constant supervision of the manager.

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